

Original Research

The Art of Teamwork: Exploring Actor Collaboration in Platform-Based Businesses

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Abstract

Platform companies have become much more important economically in recent years. Collaboration between service providers and service recipients is essential to obtaining an advantage and guaranteeing market viability. The purpose of this study was to create a collaborative behavior model for business platform development. The statistical population included both platform service providers and recipients. For the analysis, 330 service recipients and 235 service providers were randomly selected. A comprehensive review of relevant literature identified key dimensions of collaborative behavior. For service recipients, this included information seeking, information sharing, responsible behavior, and personal interaction. Similarly, for service providers, the dimensions were Organizational Citizenship Behavior, interpersonal interaction, Informational behavior, Altruistic behavior. Confirmatory factor analysis was used to assess the constructs' validity, while Cronbach's alpha coefficient and composite reliability were used to guarantee reliability. Metaheuristic methods, such as particle swarm optimization, differential evolution, artificial bee colony, genetic algorithms, and harmony search, were used to categorize platform actors according to collaborative behavior. The results showed different categories. Service providers were divided into "active and interactive service providers" and "normal and indifferent service providers," while service recipients were divided into "interactive and analytical service receivers" and "normal and indifferent service receivers," considering all aspects of collaboration.

Keywords: Collaboration, Platform Businesses, Metaheuristics.

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Introduction

A recent remarkable socio-economic development is the emergence of the platform as a business model, being named revolution sometimes. The model is changing different socio-economic issues and upgrading the performance of traditional companies, markets, and professions (Wang et al., 2017). Platforms are intermediary technologies that, instead of producing or supplying a commodity or service, make the ground for communication between agents for a specific service and product. Hagiú et al. (2014) introduce a platform as a technology-based space that provides the ground for interaction or exchange between two or more groups of distinct but interdependent users in a way that the existence of every group in the space creates value for other groups. So, it can be said that platforms are intermediaries that create value by making direct interactions between two or more groups of users (Evans et al., 2008).

Platform businesses drastically influence businesses; the notable thing however is that the long-lasting consequences of this platform revolution are not clear. Therefore, to minimize negative consequences, we have to search for look for developing platforms. Moreover, among the unique features of platforms is that as much as owners can develop platforms, the service providers and receivers can also play a role in this regard and help develop platforms (Reillier, 2017). So, appropriate use of the capabilities of service providers and receivers for formulating new frameworks and thought patterns would help businesses achieve their goals. A way to achieve this goal is by focusing on the collaborative behavior of service providers and receivers. Collaborative behaviors are the ones expected and required for success in providing services. In a broader sense, collaborative behavior refers to all forms of engagement and communication over value creating process (Groth, 2005).

This study tried to design a collaborative behavior model of service providers and receivers to help the development of the platform. Focusing on the collaborative behavior of service providers and receivers, and applying CFA and metaheuristic clustering to platform businesses, this study offers a novel, data-driven approach to distinguish between service providers and receivers. This study also tried to help the designers as much as possible. These kinds of studies give platform owners the necessary opportunity to be more successful in developing the platform and to attract as many users as possible in the dynamic and highly competitive environment, where success requires a very good understanding of service providers and receivers.

Literature Review

Platform development

The European Union defines a platform as a service through which users are connected to suppliers of higher levels of the value chain. The definition highlights that the platform has many dimensions. It has also been introduced as a technological infrastructure made for providing or consolidating services by service providers for the users (Nooren et al., 2018). Therefore, platforms have the essential role of providing a system for the interaction of various groups of users (Eisenmann et al., 2009). Simply speaking, a platform is a business model that provides value-creating interactions between service

providers and receivers usually through a technological infrastructure (Kim, 2016). Service receivers are individuals, communities, businesses, or institutions that have access to the value provided by service providers and can use it and service providers are individuals, communities, businesses, or institutions that provide the value created through the platform. It is worth noting that now service providers and receivers remarkably influence the performance of platforms and act as driving forces. So, focusing on and studying their performance and behavior will drastically help platform development, and collaborative behavior is a way to a competitive advantage (Bave et al., 2009).

Several recent studies, including those by Mady et al. (2025), Li et al. (2025), Topalova et al. (2024) and Raco et al. (2024), have thoroughly investigated the development of platforms, providing valuable insights into the underlying mechanisms, challenges, and emerging trends in this domain.

Collaborative behavior

Collaboration means “working together”, and is a complex and multidimensional concept, and has been defined differently (Brophy, 2008). Some experts have introduced it as an outcome (Nelson et al., 2008), and some as a process (Heatley & Kruske, 2011); a specific process or processes that occur over interactions. So, we can say that collaboration is a process through which people can change things, and themselves, be part of the change.

Cermak et al. (1994) define collaboration as such specific behaviors as customers' effort or their mental, emotional, and physical intervention regarding a service. Collaboration is a complicated and multidimensional structure. In a broad sense, collaborative behavior in all its forms is the involvement and interaction in the process of creating values. Moreover, Yang et al. (2014) believe that the collaboration of service receivers in the process is beneficial not only for them but also for service providers. Therefore, both service providers and service receivers experience win-win conditions from two-sided cooperation and this will improve relations, result in service improvement (Heinonen et al., 2013), and finally increase market share and profit (Dagger et al., 2007). Moreover, exploring the collaboration of customers is not a new issue, since its importance lies in creating a competitive advantage against competitors and promoting businesses (Vargo & Lusch, 2008). It is noteworthy that collaborative behavior is affected by various factors and conditions inside and outside the system and their effectiveness differs according to the type of the system. Therefore, knowing behaviors is so significant for making effective decisions and influencing performance and satisfaction (Yi et al., 2011).

Several recent studies, including those by Türetken et al. (2025), Pricopoaia et al. (2023), Maddah and Heydari (2024) and Blay et al. (2024), have thoroughly investigated the Collaborative behavior, providing valuable insights into the underlying mechanisms, challenges, and emerging trends in this domain.

Methods

The procedure for conducting this applied research (after stating the problem and purposes of the study) is as follows (Figure 1):

Identifying various dimensions of collaborative behavior of platform service providers and receivers

Reviewing the related literature and conducting an extensive study on the theoretical issues resulted in determining and considering the following dimensions of collaborative behavior of platform service providers and service receivers (Table 1).

Table 1. Dimensions of collaborative behavior of platform service providers and receivers

Collaborative behavior	Dimensions	References
Collaborative behavior of service receivers	Information searching Information sharing Responsible behavior Personal interaction	Chen and Raab, 2014. Yi & Gong, 2013. Bove et al., 2009. Rodie and Kleine, 2000.
Collaborative behavior of service providers	Organizational Citizenship Behavior interpersonal interaction Informational behavior Altruistic behavior	Organ, 1998. Kelley et al., 1990. Kellogg, et al., 1997.

Determining the statistical population and participants of the sample

The statistical population consists of Instagram platform service providers and receivers, and the sampling method is random sampling. Since there was no exact data on the number of platform service providers and receivers, the size of the sample was determined using the unlimited population equation:

$$n = \frac{S^2 * Z_{\alpha}^2}{d^2}$$

where, S^2 is the variance of the initial sample, which is calculated initially by distributing 30 questionnaires. Since this research was done at a 95% confidence level, Z is 1.96, and d (the value of unavoidable random error for measuring variable observations in the population) is 0.05 (Table 2).

Table 2 shows that 330 participants were selected as service receivers and 235 participants as service providers.

Table 2. The sample size of service providers and receivers

Platform user	Number of data	Average	Variance	Confidence level	Unavoidable random error	Sample size
Service receiver	30	4.36	0.215	1.96	0.05	330
Service provider	30	4.56	0.153	1.96	0.05	235

Validity of the collaborative behavior questionnaire of platform service providers and receivers

To see whether the items of collaborative behavior of platform service providers and receivers, as measures, are placed in a specific construct, confirmatory factor analysis was used. If factor loadings between latent and observable variables are higher than 0.4, the items have good explanatory ability, also T-Value shows the significance of the correlation between variables. If the value is more than the absolute value of 1.96 (because significance is calculated at the 5% error level), the parameters of the model are significant. Table 3 and Table 4 show the results of the confirmatory factor analysis of the collaborative behavior items of platform service providers and receivers

Table 3. The results of the confirmatory factor analysis of the collaborative behavior items of service receivers

Item (structure)	Measure	Factor loading	T-Value
Information searching	Receiving information on platform services from others	0.58	9.60
	Paying close attention to others' behaviors to use better the services of a platform	0.80	13.05
	Getting the internet address of the required platform from others	0.44	7.27
Information Sharing	Clearly stating expectations from service providers	0.62	11.71
	Giving information to platform service providers if necessary	0.77	15.45
	Giving information to platform service providers for the betterment of the service	0.80	16.28
Responsible behavior	Answering service provider's questions about the service	0.71	14.03
	Fulfilling all duties regarding service receiving	0.76	15.59
	Having all expected behaviors while receiving a service	0.78	15.98
	Following all regulations of the platform	0.75	15.07
	Carefully doing all responsibilities while receiving a service	0.72	14.69

Item (structure)	Measure	Factor loading	T-Value
Personal interaction	Friendly behavior with platform service providers	0.78	16.35
	Kind behavior with platform service providers	0.81	17.43
	Polite behavior with platform service providers	0.84	18.27
	Respectful behavior with platform service providers	0.80	17.02
	Non-aggressive behavior with platform service providers	0.59	11.22

Table 4. The results of the confirmatory factor analysis of the collaborative behavior items of service providers

Item (structure)	Measure	Factor loading	T-Value
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	Answering service receiver's questions about the service	0.71	12.01
	Fulfilling all duties regarding providing the service	0.80	14.13
	Having all expected behaviors while providing the service	0.79	13.90
	Following all defined procedures for providing the service	0.71	12.01
interpersonal interaction	Carefully doing responsibilities while providing a service	0.75	12.94
	Friendly behavior with platform service receivers	0.67	11.15
	Kind behavior with platform service receivers	0.77	13.54
	Polite behavior with platform service receivers	0.83	15.06
	Respectful behavior with platform service receivers	0.78	13.80
	Non-aggressive behavior with platform service receiver	0.66	11.03
Informational behavior	Giving useful information about the platform to others	0.73	12.20
	Answering online or offline questions on the platform	0.68	11.10
	Giving necessary information to others in line with accuracy requires	0.81	14.09
	Helping new service providers adapt to the platform environment	0.91	14.42

Item (structure)	Measure	Factor loading	T-Value
Altruistic behavior	Helping other service providers solve problems about providing platform services	0.91	17.51
	The tendency to coordinate and communicate with other platform service providers	0.82	14.75
	The tendency to help other platform service providers in doing their duties	0.70	11.94

Since the value of loading related to each item (service providers and service receivers) is more than 0.4, there is an agreement between the obtained results of this research and the theoretical structure, and all the main components of the research are confirmed. Moreover, since the T-value values of all cases are more than 1.96, all the parameters of the model are significant.

Reliability of the collaborative behavior questionnaire of platform service providers and receivers

Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability were used to confirm the reliability of the items on the collaborative behavior of service providers and receivers. Table 5 shows the results.

Table 5. The results of the reliability test are based on Cronbach's alpha and the composite reliability of the collaborative behavior of service providers and receivers.

Collaborative behavior	Cronbach's alpha coefficient	Composite reliability
Service receivers	0.937	0.947
Service providers	0.959	0.960

Table 5 shows that Cronbach's alpha for the items of collaborative behavior of service receivers is 0.937, the value of composite reliability is 0.947, Cronbach's alpha for the expectations of service providers is 0.959 and the value of composite reliability is 0.960. This shows the excellent internal consistency of the items and the reliability of the measurement tool.

Clustering based on metaheuristic algorithms

Clustering is categorizing participants into groups of people who have similar characteristics, and members of different clusters are completely different from each other (Han & Kamber, 2011). Clustering is complicated when the number of clusters is unknown and the clustering algorithm tries to find the number of clusters. This is called automatic clustering. One way of solving an automatic clustering problem is turning it into an optimization problem and then solving it by applying intelligent and evolutionary optimization algorithms (Das, et al., 2008). The behavior of platform actors is nonlinear, multidimensional, and characterized by correlations among constructs. This complexity results in a multi-peak landscape that classical methods struggle to navigate fully. In

contrast, metaheuristic approaches, with their extensive search capabilities and solution diversification, offer a more effective means of analyzing and optimizing complex behaviors on platforms. Here, “particle swarm optimization”, “differential evolution”, “artificial bee colony”, “harmony search”, and “genetic” algorithms were used. To make the clustering problem an optimization one, evaluation indices are needed. DB indices (Davies & Bouldin, 1979) and CS index (Chou, et al., 2004) were used in this study.

Figure 1. Research procedure

Findings

Information of participants

Table 6 shows the demographic information of service providers.

Table 6. The demographic information of participants (service providers and receivers)

Demographic information of respondents		Service receivers		Service providers	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	109	33	166	70.6
	Female	221	67	69	29.4
Marital status	Single	152	46.1	121	51.5
	Married	178	53.9	114	48.5
Education	Diploma and lower	58	17.6	33	14
	Associate degree	60	18.2	32	13.6
	Bachelor's degree	136	41.2	103	43.8
	Postgraduate degree	76	23	67	28.6
Age	Younger than 25	121	36.7	99	42.1
	26-35	114	34.5	69	29.4
	36-45	72	21.8	48	20.4
	46-55	22	6.7	17	7.2
	Older than 55	1	0.3	2	0.9

Clustering

Clustering service receivers

Categorizing service receivers having common characteristics into smaller groups helps better decision-making. To cluster service receivers, “particle swarm optimization”, “differential evolution”, “artificial bee colony”, “harmony search”, and “genetic” algorithms and DB and CS indices were. Table 7 shows the final results of the cluster analysis of the participants.

Table 7. Cluster analysis of service receivers using five rhythm patterns and two indicators

Algorithm	DB index	CS index
Particle swarm optimization (PSO)	0.68736	0.53534
Differential evolution (DE)	0.6950	0.53534
Artificial bee colony (ABC)	0.66961	0.53534
Harmony search (HSA)	0.75403	0.53534
Genetic (GA)	0.72267	0.53534
The frequency of every algorithm is 500.		

The data in Table 7 regarding the cluster analysis of service receivers based on five algorithms and two indices, shows that all algorithms based on the CS index after five hundred iterations of the equation converge at a value of 0.53534 (the best possible value). Moreover, as Figure 2 shows, stopping was determined to be the convergence of the equation to stop the designed algorithms.

Figure 2. Particle swarm optimization algorithm, differential evolution, artificial bee colony, and harmony search (receivers)

After cluster analysis with five optimal metaheuristic algorithms, Table 8 shows the results of clustering based on information search, information sharing, responsible behavior, and personal interaction. Considering that automatic clustering was used to determine the number of clusters, two clusters were determined for every algorithm. Table 8 includes the average dimensions of the collaborative behavior of service receivers, the rank in the cluster, the rank among the clusters, and the average of the entire clusters based on the dimensions of collaborative behavior.

Table 8. The final results of the cluster analysis of service receivers using the meta-initiative rhythms Algorithm

Cluster	Dimension	Information searching	Information Sharing	Responsible behavior	Personal interaction	Average
1	Average	3.3453	3.9828	3.8936	4.0942	3.8290
	Rank in the cluster	4	2	3	1	
	Rank among the clusters	1	1	1	1	
2	Average	1.9167	1.9167	1.9167	1.9167	1.9167
	Rank in the cluster	1	1	1	1	
	Rank among the clusters	2	2	2	2	

After running automatic cluster analysis, the clusters should be named to understand them better. The naming is done considering the characteristics of each cluster and different dimensions of collaborative behavior, the opinion of the experts.

- Interactive and analytical service receivers: Personal interaction is the most important dimension in this cluster, information searching is the second, and information searching is the least important one. For members of this cluster of service receivers, such behaviors as carefully doing the responsibilities while receiving services, friendly behavior, kind behavior, polite behavior, respectful behavior, and not being aggressive are the most significant behaviors facing platform service providers. Such behaviors as getting information from others about platform services, paying close attention to others' behavior for better usage of platform services, and asking others about the internet address of needed platforms are less important. Moreover, all dimensions of expectations are the most significant ones compared to another cluster for the service receivers of this cluster.

- Normal and indifferent service receivers regarding all dimensions of collaboration: All dimensions of collaborative behavior in this cluster including information searching, information sharing, responsible behavior, and personal interaction are equally important. Moreover, all dimensions of collaboration have the least importance compared to the other clusters.

Clustering service providers

Decision-making can benefit from clustering service providers having common characteristics into smaller groups. To cluster service providers, particle swarm optimization, differential evolution, artificial bee colony, genetic, and harmony search algorithms, and DB and CS evaluation indices were used. Table 9 shows the final results of the cluster analysis of service providers.

Table 9. Cluster analysis of service providers with five rhythm algorithms and two indices

Algorithm	DB index	CS index
Particle swarm optimization (PSO)	0.69254	0.52399
Differential evolution (DE)	0.60807	0.52399
Artificial bee colony (ABC)	0.58415	0.52399
Harmony (HAS)	0.73945	0.52399
Genetic (GA)	0.69755	0.52399
The frequency of every Algorithm is 500.		

Table 9 shows the data on cluster analysis of service providers based on five algorithms “particle swarm optimization (PSO)”, “differential evolution (DE)”, “artificial bee colony (ABC)”, “genetic Algorithm (G)”, and “harmony search (HS)” and DB and CS indices, it is evident that algorithms based on the CS index converge after five hundred iterations of the equation at a value of 0.52399 (the best possible value). Moreover, as Figure 3 shows, stopping was determined to be the convergence of the equation to stop the designed algorithms.

Figure 3. Particle swarm optimization algorithm, differential evolution, artificial bee colony, and harmony search (service providers)

Table 10 shows the results of clustering the dimensions of Organizational Citizenship Behavior, interpersonal interaction, Informational behavior, Altruistic behavior. Since the automatic clustering method was used to determine the number of clusters, the number of clusters in each of the five algorithms is two clusters. For each of the clusters, the average collaborative behavior of service providers, the rank in that cluster, and the rank among the clusters were determined. Moreover, the average of all clusters on the dimensions of collaborative behavior of service providers is determined.

Table 10. The final results of cluster analysis of service providers with metaheuristic algorithms

Cluster	Dimension	Organizational Citizenship Behavior	interpersonal interaction	Informational behavior	Altruistic behavior	Average
1	Average	4.0182	4.1660	4.0342	3.9188	4.0343
	Rank in the cluster	3	1	2	4	
	Rank among the clusters	1	1	1	1	
2	Average	2.2292	2.2292	2.2292	2.2292	2.2292
	Rank in the cluster	1	1	1	1	
	Rank among the clusters	2	2	2	2	

After doing automatic cluster analysis, the clusters should be named to understand them better. The naming is done considering the characteristics of each cluster regarding different dimensions of collaborative behavior based on the opinions of experts.

Active and interactive service providers: interpersonal interaction is the most important dimension in this cluster, informational behavior is the second one, and altruistic behavior is the least important dimension (the difference of the average of dimensions that are the basis of ranking is very low). For the members of this cluster of service providers, such behaviors as doing responsibilities carefully while providing services, friendly behavior, kind behavior, polite behavior, respectful behavior, and non-aggressive behavior when facing platform users are of high importance. However, such behaviors as helping new service providers adapt to the platform environment, helping other service providers solve problems of providing platform services, the tendency to coordinate and communicate with other platform service providers, and the tendency to help them are less important than other behavioral components. It should be noted that for members of this cluster, all dimensions of collaboration are of the utmost importance compared to the other cluster.

Normal and indifferent service providers in all dimensions of collaboration: In this cluster, all dimensions of collaboration, including Organizational Citizenship Behavior, interpersonal interaction, Informational behavior, Altruistic behavior are equally

important. At the same time, for members of this cluster, all dimensions of collaboration are of the least importance compared to the other cluster.

Conclusions

Globalization of activities and the liberal international economy have forced platform owners to improve continuously their competitive competencies. Collaborative behavior is a vital strategic factor in this regard that, through collaborative action, results in desired outcomes. This applied research tried to design a model of collaborative behavior of service receivers in line with the development of platforms. After reviewing the related literature, the theoretical foundations and confirmed by experts, the dimensions “information searching”, “information sharing”, “responsible behavior”, and “personal interaction” were determined for the collaborative behavior of service receivers and “Organizational Citizenship Behavior”, “interpersonal interaction”, “informational behavior”, and “altruistic behavior” were determined as dimensions collaborative behavior of service providers. Then, a researcher-made questionnaire was designed to cluster service providers and service receivers. The validity of the questionnaire was checked using confirmatory factor analysis and its reliability was confirmed using Cronbach’s alpha and composite reliability. For automatic clustering, five optimization algorithms, that is, “particle swarm”, “differential evolution”, “artificial bee colony”, “genetic”, and “harmony search”, and DB and CS indices were used. Regarding service receivers, “interactive and analytical service receivers” and “normal and indifferent” regarding all dimensions of collaboration were identified. Regarding service providers, “active and interactive” and “normal and indifferent in all dimensions of collaboration” clusters were identified. The procedure of this research is systematic and has defined steps. This feature makes everything clear for other researchers and managers working in this field and assures them that by following the steps, they can achieve the expected results. Moreover, paying attention to the collaborative behavior of service providers and receivers is of high importance because by having the necessary information, following the regulations about platforms, and feeling cordial, they will help platform owners understand their needs and desires. Since collaborative behavior is a factor that makes systems dynamic and productive, knowing the results of this research can help researchers and platform owners tackle the challenges of current highly competitive and unstable conditions and find practical solutions for the development.

Further Researches

This research explored the collaborative behavior of service providers and receivers by studying the related literature, but over time the items of collaborative behavior will change as platforms change. Therefore, it is suggested that for using this model in the future, the components of collaborative behavior be adjusted according to the changes.

Both service providers and service receivers need some tools and services to encourage collaborative behavior. So, preparing a cognitive map of the probable tools and services of each group can be effective for easily joining and working on platforms.

It is also suggested that future studies focus on such issues as the way of developing interactions between platform service providers and service receivers for increasing

collaboration, the impact of the culture of communities on the collaboration of platform service providers and receivers, and the consequences of collaborative behavior of platform service providers.

References

- Blay, T., Froese, F. J., Taras, V., & Gunkel, M. (2024). Convergence of collaborative behavior in virtual teams: The role of external crises and implications for performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 109(4), 469–489. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0001133>
- Bove, L. L., Pervan, S. J., Beatty, S. E., & Shiu, E. (2009). Service worker role in encouraging customer organizational citizenship behaviors. *Journal of Business Research*, 62(7), 698–705. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2008.07.003>
- Brophy, S. (2008). Making the case for case study research. *Nursing Council of New Zealand*, 14(11), 2-20. PMID: 19117111.
- Cermak, D. S. P., File, K. M., & Prince, R. A. (1994). Customer Participation in Service Specification and Delivery. *Journal of Applied Business Research (JABR)*, 10(2), 90–97. <https://doi.org/10.19030/jabr.v10i2.5942>
- Chen, S. C., & Raab, C. (2014). Construction and Validation of the Customer Participation Scale. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 41(2), 131-153. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1096348014525631>
- Chou, CH., Su, MC. & Lai, E. (2004). A new cluster validity measure and its application to image compression. *Pattern Anal Applic* 7(2), 205–220. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10044-004-0218-1>
- Dagger, T. S., Sweeney, J. C., & Johnson, L. W. (2007). A Hierarchical Model of Health Service Quality: Scale Development and Investigation of an Integrated Model. *Journal of Service Research*, 10(2), 123-142. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094670507309594>
- Das, S., Abraham, A., and Konar, A. (2008). Automatic Clustering Using an Improved Differential Evolution Algorithm, in *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics - Part A: Systems and Humans*, 38(1), 218-237. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMCA.2007.909595>
- Davies, D. L., and Bouldin, D. W., (1979). A cluster separation measure, in *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 1(2), 224-227. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.1979.4766909>
- Eisenmann. T. R., Parker, G., and Van Alstyne M. (2009). Opening platforms: How, When, and Why? *Platforms*. This paper has been published under the same title as Chapter 6 in *Platforms, Markets & Innovation*, Harvard Business School Entrepreneurial Management Working Paper No. 09-030, 131-162. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1264012>

- Evans, David & Schmalensee, Richard. (2008). Markets with Two-Sided Platforms. *Issues in Competition Law and Policy*, 1. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1094820>
- Groth, M. (2005). Customers as Good Soldiers: Examining Citizenship Behaviors in Internet Service Deliveries. *Journal of Management*, 31(1), 7-27. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206304271375>
- Hagiu, Andrei and Halaburda, Hanna (2014). Information and two-sided platform profits, *International Journal of Industrial Organization*, Elsevier, 34, 25-35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijindorg.2014.04.001>
- Han, J. and Kamber, M. (2011) *Data Mining: Concepts and Techniques*. 2nd Edition, Morgan Kaufmann Publishers, San Francisco.
- Heatley, M., and Kruske, S. (2011). Defining collaboration in Australian maternity care. *Woman Birth*, 24(2), 53-57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wombi.2011.02.002>
- Heinon, K., Strandvik, T. and Voima, P. (2013). Customer dominant value formation in service. *European Business Review*, 25(2), 104-123. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09555341311302639>
- Kelley, S. W., Donnelly, J. H., and Skinner, S. J. (1990). Customer participation in service production and delivery. *Journal of Retailing*, 66(33), 315-335.
- Kellogg, D.L., Youngdahl, W.E. and Bowen, D.E. (1997). On the relationship between customer participation and satisfaction: two frameworks, *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 8(3), 206-219. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09564239710185406>
- Kim, Junic. (2016). *The platform business model and strategy: a dynamic analysis of the value chain and platform business*. Thesis for PhD Business and Management, 1-360.
- Li, H., Zhang, G., Liu, H., & Feng, J. (2025). Cloud Platform Business Scenario Modeling Based on Multi-Model Fusion Recommendation Algorithm. *International Journal of High-Speed Electronics and Systems*, 34(1), 2540083. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S012915642540083X>.
- Maddah, N., & Heydari, B. (2024). Platform-driven collaboration patterns: Structural evolution over time and scale. *IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems*, 11(6), 7814–7829. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCSS.2024.3452028>
- Mady, K., Anwar, I., Boomage, M., & Sulub, M. A. (2025). Digital entrepreneurial platform capability: instrument development and validation, and its impact on entrepreneurial performance. *Technology in Society*, 102886. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2025.102886>.
- Nelson, G. A., King, M.L., & Brodine, S. (2008). Nurse-physician collaboration on medical-surgical units. *Medsurg Nurs*, 17(1), 35-40. PMID: 18429539

- Nooren, P., Van Grop, N., Van Eijk, N., and Fathaigh, R. (2018). Should we regulate digital platforms? A new framework for evaluating policy options, *Policy & Internet*, 10(3), 264-301. <https://doi.org/10.1002/poi3.177>
- Organ, D.W. (1998). *Organization citizenship behavior: The good soldier syndrome*. Lexington Books.
- Pricopoaia, O., Cristache, N., Maftai, C. O., Matis, C., & Faur, C. (2023). Modelling consumer behaviour on online collaborative platforms. *Risk in Contemporary Economy*, 205–218. <https://doi.org/10.35219/rce20670532163>
- Raco, J. R., Raton, Y., Tumewu, T. W., Raco, B., & Widjaja, I. (2024). Strategic Development of Online Business Platform Using AHP and QFD: A Case Study of Manado City, Indonesia. *Futurity Economics & Law*, 4(1), 64-86. <https://doi.org/10.57125/FEL.2024.03.25.05>.
- Reillier, L.C., & Reillier, B. (2017). *Platform Strategy: How to Unlock the Power of Communities and Networks to Grow Your Business* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315598949>
- Rodie, A., & Kleine, S. (2000). Customer participation in services production and delivery. In T. A. Swartz, D. Iacobucci (Eds.) *Customer participation in services production and delivery* (pp. 111-126). SAGE Publications, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452231327.n10>
- Topalova, I., Lozova, T., Riepnova, T., Dashchenko, N., Chudaieva, I., & Darushyn, O. (2024). Business Process Management in Entrepreneurial Activity Based on a Platform Approach. *Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services*, 14(2), 46-55. <https://doi.org/10.51983/ijiss-2024.14.2.08>.
- Turetken, O., Ozkan, B., Grefen, P. (2024). Designing Collaborative Business Models for Sustainable Digital Solutions: The Case of a Shared-Micromobility Service. In: van de Wetering, R., et al. *Disruptive Innovation in a Digitally Connected Healthy World. I3E 2024. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 14907. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-72234-9_26
- Vargo, S.L., Lusch, R.F. (2008). Service-dominant logic: continuing the evolution. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 36(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-007-0069-6>
- Wang, X., Cenamor, J., Parker, G., & Van Alstyne, M. (2017). Unraveling platform strategies: A review from an organizational ambidexterity perspective. *Sustainability*, 9(5), Article 734. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9050734>
- Yang, C. C., Chen, P. S., & Chien, Y. H. (2014). Customer expertise, affective commitment, customer participation, and loyalty in B & B services. *International Journal of Organizational Innovation*, 6(4), 174-183.

Yi, Y., Nair, R., & Gong, T. (2011). Customer participation and citizenship behavioral influences on employee performance, satisfaction, commitment, and turnover intention. *Journal of Business Research*, 64(1), 87-95.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2010.02.006>

Yi, Youjae, Y. & Gong, Taeshik, (2013). "Customer value co-creation behavior: Scale development and validation," *Journal of Business Research*, Elsevier, 66(9), 1279-1284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2012.02.026>

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